

Turkish Olympic, National, International and Professional Weightlifters Perform Resistance Zones (Load and Repetition) on Autoregulation Resistance Training Periodization

Yeliz Kahraman¹, Aykut Hocalar², Alay Kesler³, İshak Göçer⁴, Birol Ünsal⁵

***Correspondence:**

Yeliz Kahraman

PhD. Yeliz KAHRAMAN, Akdeniz University and Health Science Institute, Pınarbaşı Konyaaltı, 05078, Antalya, Turkey.
yelizkahramana@hotmail.com

¹PhD. Akdeniz University and Health Science Institute, Antalya, Turkey,
yelizkahramana@hotmail.com;
orcid: 0000-0001-8209-4087

²Ph.d. Akdeniz University, Health Science Institute, Antalya, Turkey,
aykuthocalar@gmail.com. Orcid: 0009-0009-5708-4683

³Associate. İstanbul Cerrahpaşa University and Sport Science Faculty, İstanbul, Turkey,
alayk@hotmail.com. Orcid: 0000-0002-7232-6072

⁴Ph.d. Ankara University and Sport Science Faculty, Ankara, Turkey,
ishakgocer71@gmail.com. Orcid: 0000-0002-2337-2240

⁵Associate. Akdeniz University and Sport Science Faculty, Antalya, Turkey,
bunsal@akdeniz.edu.tr. Orcid: 0009-0009-8765-5301

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Abstract

Introduction. Muscular contraction load and repetition strategies are knowing to continuum zone repetition method (endurance 50% – hypertrophy 70% – strength – 85%) provide auto-regulated training volume, to detect muscular working load and repetition one set sections, one of muscle exercise condition. The muscle contraction potential gain is auto-regulated working principle as seperately high load low repetition and low load high repetition.

Objective. The aim of this study was to detect muscular contraction performance level of weightlifters, to perform continuum zone repetition method on autoregulation resistance training periodization.

Materials and methods. The weightlifters; 8 men and women, participated over short week 3 week and 2 day autoregulation resistance training periodization performed on (10RM) hypertrophy zone and (6RM) power zone in weekly day to day plan. The continuum zone repetition method measures formed one repetition maximum (1RM), 50%1RM low load – repetition, 70%1RM moderate load – repetition, and 85%1RM high load – repetition on weekly and daily non-linear muscle concentric load detection.

Results. For autoregulation resistance training, one repetition maximum outcomes on countermovement jump shrug and bent-over row increased, however, isometric deadlift and overhead press was not increase significant. The load increased and repetition decreased outcomes in different muscle exercise condition.

Conclusion. Muscular exercise resistance zone periodization and contraction concentric load program improve to weightlifters, however, study performed as muscular adaptation outcomes on short term autoregulation performance as loading increase and repetition decrease. The outcomes concluded to autoregulation resistance training periodization to enable maximizing muscular contraction level able increased concentric load and high exercise condition repetition set-up.

Keywords Continuum zone repetition, autoregulation resistance training, short term periodization, weightlifters

The experimental study non-controlled study included in autoregulation resistance training periodization.

- The study was performed in sport-hall.
- Sporting and funding no supported addition no published in other journals.
- The study aim was to perform autoregulation resistance training promotes maximum number of repetition and concentric load in weightlifters.

Authors stated to study initially first will published in journal, ethic committee proved to study, firstly experimental condition applied in weightlifters.

Professional athletes accedeed to performing of resistance training periodization.

- Authors stated to no decleration and no conflict of interests.

Introduction

Olympic weightlift performance daily program and plan consist of snatch and clean & jerk lift resistance weight-lift strength and techniques. Snatch technique able into a top position where the legs are extended and locked simultaneously while the clean and jerk techniques initially a position where the weight is lifted from the floor to the chest and locked above the head. The resistance training and muscular exercise condition, to weightlifters previously performed on day to day periodization setting related muscular contraction potential gain and strength performance adjusted for one set-up load and repetition manipulation and multi joint exercise condition (ACSM, 2009; Kahraman et al., 2024). Manipulation concentric load and repetition exercises are single set and multi joint exercise condition as this manipulative muscle exercise condition and performance level perform on low load high repetition or high load low repetition terms of load and repetition method thenbefore resistance training guidelines, thus strength and resistance training working principles can be prescribed to one set set-up and changing rest interval principles to weightlifters (Kahraman & Varol, 2024; Kreamer & Ratamess, 2004; Schoenfeld et al., 2015). Performance level of individual's resistance training is determine as continuum zone repetition or muscular strength-endurance regimes for muscle adaptation and maximum number of repetition to enable auto-regulated resistance training within non-linear day to day and weekly program (Kahraman, 2023; Greig et al., 2021). Previously, resistance training periodization and plan are compared to developing of high load increases as performing maximize strength performance level in single set set-ups has been aimed to high load muscular fibril composition whereas low load increases muscle mass (Kahraman et al., 2024). Thus, have been uncleared to strength-endurance program to reflect continuum zone repetition method performing high-moderate-low load one repetition maximum (Kahraman & Varol, 2024). One of continuum zone repetition method (Schoenfeld et al., 2021), is autoregulation resistance training provides load and repetition adaptation in selection periodizate model to maximize muscle concentric contraction performance level in selected exercise program, addition adjust for resistance zone prescription in daily and non-linear weekly periodization (Mann et al., 2010; Kahraman & Varol, 2024). Autoregulation resistance training was not used in muscle performance level of training periodization for weightlifters prescribed as exercise selection, intensity, set, rest interval, for daily and weekly individual performance level (Kahraman et al., 2024; Kahraman & Varol, 2024). Repetitive auto-regulated loading training contents provide manipulated set and rest interval to short and long term resistance periodization including formed on the exercise condition (Nevin, 2019; Kahraman, 2024). Reviews reported that autoregulation resistance training contents have promoted to exercise periodization of all seasons and regimes are (1-3 weeks) micro, (1 to 2 months) macro and (+12 week) long periodization (Kahraman, 2024; Greig et al., 2021). With this training to muscle contraction force and training volume outcomes can able weekly loading and repetition decreases into 12 week (Graham & Cleather, 2021). Periodized models were noted on muscle strength-endurance regimes to determine total number of repetition and next training loading to multiple combination setting set-up in autoregulation of strength-endurance zone 12RM, hypertrophy zone 10RM, power zone 6RM and strength zone 3RM (Suchomel et al., 2021). For example, periodized model power zone periodization was used in to auto-regulated load and repetition session to provide explosive power in short term micro periodization performed on 6RM pre plan including of CMJ and SJ showed increases as compared traditional linear 70% 1RM squat and bench press exercise condition (Huang et al., 2023). The muscle resistance efforts have been enable to maximize muscle strength performance as muscle metabolic adaptation and loading

stress factor in specific repetition and rest interval levels (ACSM, 2009). In this direction, auto-regulated working principle in generally included 3 to 5 rest intervals (>90% 1RM – 3RM) in high load to manipulated load and repetition whereas 1-2 min rest intervals to manipulated sets on other zone regimes (Nevin, 2019; Suchomel et al., 2021). However, indeed 1 min rest intervals constant method whereas 3 to 5 min rest intervals promote reliable muscle strength manipulation in other zone regimes resistance training periodization and plan (Kahraman, 2024). In load and repetition changes were used to multiple sets (2 to 5 set) evaluated on constant rest intervals not used in different continuum zone repetition autoregulation resistance training periodization unallow to muscular strength-endurance adaptation on unfatigue accumulation. In this resistance conditions for this study not performed on load and repetition changes in continuum zone repetition methods by muscle concentric load and strength-endurance gains in short week performance outcomes on weightlifters.

Therefore, our hypothesis was to research muscle strength and endurance performance outcomes from autoregulation resistance training periodization in weightlifters. Basical hypothesis was to investigate continuum zone repetition method to maximize muscle performance outcomes by autoregulation resistance training in weightlifters. This study aim was to investigate weightlifters in maximize muscle strength performance outcomes by continuum zone repetition method autoregulation resistance training periodization.

Material and Methods

Subjects

The population sample size was determined as the one priori sample size method to $n=8$ power of the study is $(1-\beta \text{ prob}) 0.95$ and $\alpha\text{-error prob } 0.05$. Experimental resolvment and analysis were provided on comparison measures to, within paired-t test. In the descriptive analysis was to one variable was effect size: 1.20; actual power: 0.95 with variable output parameters, addition to test on the one group and two measurement as noncentrality parameter – 19.15 critical t – 2.20 (G. Power 3.1.9.7) (Table 1). In this condition, weightlifters 3 week resistance training program (2 day session of week-1) was performed under the direct supervisions of resistance training specialists. The weightlifters included in random population Turkey sample and properties of weightlifters were provided on Table 1. For this study experimental protocol permission accedeed on Akdeniz University Medicine Ethic Committee No: TBAEK-205.

Table 1. Properties of weightlifters

	Height	Weight	Age	Training year
Mean (SD)	1.67 (0.10 m)	65.62 (17.22 kg)	17.12 (2.85 y)	3.87 (1.70 y)
Min	1.50 m	49 kg	15 y	2 y
Max	1.80 m	100 kg	24 y	7 y
CV	0.06	0.26	0.16	0.44

Experimental approach to problem

The continuum zone repetition method 1. Endurance 50%, 2. Hypertrophy 70% and strength 85% were tested and weekly model auto-regulation resistance training periodization performed after test condition. Pre and post experimental test condition of study were continuum zone repetition method into 1 week and 2 days separately and autoregulation load and repetition determination tested after the anthropometry measurement, one repetition maximum (1RM), muscle fibril composition (85%1RM), local muscular endurance (50-70%1RM) load and repetition into 1 setting loading increase method within 24 – 48 hours. Ranges of weekly model autoregulation periodization applied on 2 day changing on hypertrophy zone and power zone programmes with general weightlift performances. Then, experimental desing formed on hypertrophy zone 10RM and power zone 6RM without 3 maximal weightlift resistance training. Maximize performance outcomes were reported on post measurement after 4 week.

Exercise condition

Bent-over row: Weightlift load increase condition with the barbell, the lower body muscles power work together with the leg muscles and both hamstring and quadriceps muscles are flexed linearly at the knee level with eccentric and concentric contraction phases. The exercise is performed in the upper body's standing position and the trunk position is adjusted according to contracted elbow position. The elbow position is not in the contraction starting position and the trunk region is not flexed.

Isometric deadlift: Weightlift strength and isometric strength performance used to loadable power capacity in a fixed position, this version is fixed in height, and the muscles perform isometric contraction. In particular, lower body power and strength mainly provide lumbar and abdominal activity, isometric deadlift position is fixed in the initial muscle extension, the place is the lower body power exercise. Knees are bent as variable load, leg line knee loading stress does not rely on eccentric contraction position based on lumbar stress injury.

Countermovement jump shrug: Weightlift plyometric exercise power jump and shoulder contraction, explosive power and speed development initial extension eccentric phase repeated jump, then shoulder elevation in the concentric phase until the jump reach. The body does not bend to the injury of the lumbar region during the jump, the knees should perform the same plumb line with the ankle flexion, and should be really in the lumbar line for proper jump performance. Then slowly increase the performance in the eccentric and concentric contraction phase in the positioned starting position.

Overhead press: Shoulder and arm performances involve segment strength of upper extremities to maximum lift in a joint torque pattern to develop speed and power during the weightlift phase. Weight lift shoulder strength starts with two hands in the anatomic position of the shoulder above with the barbell. The hand nearest on the barbell is pulled to raise the head. Then, the shoulder contraction is in an elevated direction with elbow extension. The muscle coordination performed on the acromion progresses to shoulder pull at the uphead level and provides arm extension. The eyes look forward linearly at the head level providing coordination.

Autoregulation periodization

As resistance training periodization has been performed on potential plan and program to regime, session, and set-up, the continuum zone repetition performing autoregulation resistance training periodization. To determine continuum zone repetition test protocols were improved autoregulation resistance training periodization through specific properties periodic repetition strategy. Exploration of the optimize performance relationship is required continuum zone repetition strategies to evaluate strength, hypertrophy, endurance, and power session. This popular resistance zone power and strength used in the study enable to using volume, load, constant set combination in specific training section as maximal repetition set-up. Other approach for continuum zone repetition specialized training adaptation occurring heavy load strength and power exacuate to continuum dimension of repetition maximum. High repetition low load (10RM) at set-up 70-75% hypertrophy zone and low repetition high load (6RM) at set-up 80-85% power zone were performed on block, daily undulation, weekly model, non-periodic, zone and reverse periodization. In this training direction, daily and weekly power zone performance into 48 hour were performed on weekly weightlifter’s strength program. Set-up resistance strength sessions adjusted for maximize strength and continuum zone repetition method (Table 2).

Table 2. Autoregulation resistance training

Monday	POWER ZONE	Wednesday	HYPERTROPHY ZONE	Friday	Saturday	Sunday
Max strength day (snatch +clean+jerk+squat)	SETLER 30% – 10RM x 1 1. set – 10RM; 50% of 6RM 2. set – 6RM; 75% of 6RM 3. set – max.rep; 100% of 6RM 4. set – max.rep; +2.5 – 5 kg > 3 min interval	Max strength day (snatch +clean+jerk+squat)	SETLER 30% – 10RM x 1 1. set – 12RM; 50% of 10RM 2. set – 10RM; 75% of 10RM 3. set – max.rep; 100% of 10RM 4. set – max.rep; +2.5 – 5 kg > 2 min interval	Max strength day (snatch +clean+jerk+squat)	Strength+ technique+ squat	Strength+ technique+ squat

Performance level determination

Weightlift performances as snatch, clean & jerk and squat obtained from individual training maximal outcomes. Then, one repetition maximum test protocols were initially started at load percentage repetition trials (Eloika, Werksan equipment strength performance), load percentage determined on;

- 30% of 1RM – 10RM,

- 50% of 1RM – 6RM,
- 70% of 1RM – 5RM,
- 90% of 1RM – 3RM,

- then increases to 1RM – 100% added 10-20 kg lower body and 5-10 kg upper as on the 2-5 min rest intervals body until accomplishment 3 set set-up (Haff, 2016). After one repetition maximum, maximum number of repetition set –ups performed on low load – rep (50%1RM), moderate load – rep (70%1RM) and high load – rep (85%1RM) to 1 accomplishment trial after 30% 1RM – 10RM warm-up used to increased concentric load tested one day. The local muscular endurance detected on 50-70% 1RM load an repetition, to tested on 85% 1RM muscle fibril composition repetition and load setted on exercise condition. The experimental load and repetition used to autoregulation resistance training loading determination. Training days were into 48 hours and test protocols were into 24 hours performed on weightlift hall. Before, exercise conditions were tested at 10-min warm-up and body stretching and barbell low load.

Statistical analysis

On the strength variables, statistical descriptive analysis was detected on weightlifters as the population mean, standard deviation, then various tests provided normality distribution values on sample group with shapiro wilk normality test (Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012). As the normality assumption dependent variables tested on paired-t test to 2 measurement (pre and post tests) statistical analysis resolved to descriptive estimate statistical values on population. Descriptive values resolved on the statistical significant differences determined on dependent variables (p-values) (Lakens, 2013).

Results

The weightlift performance outcomes detected during autoregulation resistance training periodization. One repetition maximum outcomes resulted on bent-over row and countermovement jump shrug increased, however, deadlift and overhead press decreased in Table 3.

Table 3. One repetition maximum

	Pre	Post	CI%	t	p
Isometric deadlift	107.50 (42.67)	116.25 (42.40)	(-1.395) – (0.141)	-1.825	0.111
Countermovement jump shrug	97.50 (32.84)	108.75 (35.22)	(-2.870) – (-0.599)	-4.965	0.002
Bent-over row	85.00 (34.64)	101.25 (32.26)	(-1.944) – (-0.169)	-3.052	0.019
Overhead press	42.50 (15.81)	42.50 (16.47)	(-0.693) – (0.693)	0.000	1.000

One repetition 50%1RM load outcomes resulted on countermovement jump shrug (t=-4.965; CI%=-2.870 – -0.599; p=0.002) and bent-over row (t=-3.052; CI%= -1.944 – 0.169; p=0.019) increased, however, isometric deadlift (t=-0.143; CI%=-0.742 – 0.645; p=0.890) and overhead press (t=1.528; CI%=-0.233 – 1.270; p=0.170) not significant change. The

repetition outcomes resulted on isometric deadlift ($t=2.534$; $CI\%=0.043 - 1.706$; $p=0.039$) at significant value decreased, however, countermovement jump shrug ($t=1.888$; $CI\%=-0.124 - 1.422$; $p=0.101$), bent over row ($t=1.238$; $CI\%=-0.305 - 1.152$; $p=0.256$) and over head press ($t=1.426$; $CI\%=-0.251 - 1.228$; $p=0.197$) not significant changes.

One repetition 70%1RM load outcomes resulted on countermovement jump shrug ($t=-4.333$; $CI\%=-2.558 - -0.462$; $p=0.003$) and bent-over row ($t=-2.947$; $CI\%=-1.690 - -0.034$; $p=0.041$) increased, however, isometric deadlift ($t=-1.722$; $CI\%=-1.352 - 0.169$; $p=0.129$) and overhead press ($t=0.000$; $CI\%=-0.693 - 0.693$; $p=1.000$) not significant change. The repetition outcomes resulted on isometric deadlift ($t=3.182$; $CI\%=0.200 - 2.004$; $p=0.015$) and bent-over row ($t=3.101$; $CI\%=0.181 - 1.967$; $p=0.017$) at significant value decreased, countermovement jump shrug ($t=0.707$; $CI\%=-0.463 - 0.946$; $p=0.502$) and overhead press ($t=0.665$; $CI\%=-0.476 - 0.931$; $p=0.527$) not significant changes.

One repetition 85%1RM load outcomes resulted on isometric deadlift ($t=-2.391$; $CI\%=-1.642 - -0.007$; $p=0.048$), countermovement jump shrug ($t=-4.822$; $CI\%=-2.799 - -0.568$; $p=0.002$) and bent-over row ($t=-2.683$; $CI\%=-1.744 - -0.080$; $p=0.031$) increased, however, overhead press ($t=-0.552$; $CI\%=-0.889 - 0.512$; $p=0.598$) not significant change. The repetition outcomes resulted on isometric deadlift ($t=2.084$; $CI\%=-0.072 - 1.507$; $p=0.076$), countermovement jump shrug ($t=1.579$; $CI\%=-0.208 - 1.292$; $p=0.158$), bent-over row ($t=1.213$; $CI\%=-0.312 - 1.142$; $p=0.265$) and overhead press ($t=0.000$; $CI\%=-0.693 - 0.693$; $p=1.000$) not significant change in Table 4.

Table 4. Load and repetition outcomes

	Pre – Post	p	Pre – Post	p
	LOAD		REP	
Isometric deadlift	50%		50%	
	53.75 (21.33) – 54.37 (25.97)	0.890	19.75 (4.46) – 15.50 (4.20)	0.039
	70%		70%	
	73.12 (29.51) – 79.37 (29.45)	0.129	13.12 (3.31) – 8.75 (2.60)	0.015
Countermovement jump shrug	85%		85%	
	88.75 (35.83) – 96.87 (35.24)	0.048	8.12 (3.68) – 5.12 (2.58)	0.076
	50%		50%	
	48.75 (16.42) – 54.37 (17.61)	0.002	20.12 (11.20) – 13.37 (5.47)	0.101
Bent-over row	70%		70%	
	66.25 (22.32) – 74.37 (25.13)	0.003	12.00 (8.96) – 9.50 (3.89)	0.502
	85%		85%	
	80.00 (26.18) – 90.62 (30.05)	0.002	10.75 (6.64) – 6.50 (2.44)	0.158
Overhead press	50%		50%	
	42.50 (17.32) – 50.62 (16.13)	0.019	15.00 (4.81) – 12.37 (4.68)	0.256
	70%		70%	
	60.00 (21.38) – 68.75 (23.10)	0.041	10.75 (2.96) – 7.50 (2.56)	0.017
Overhead press	85%		85%	
	71.25 (25.87) – 83.12 (27.11)	0.031	6.87 (2.80) – 5.62 (3.20)	0.265
	50%		50%	
	21.25 (7.90) – 20.00 (5.97)	0.170	17.75 (6.69) – 14.37 (3.73)	0.197

	70%		70%	
	28.12 (10.32) – 28.12 (10.99)	1.000	10.25 (3.37) – 9.37 (1.18)	0.527
	85%		85%	
	33.75 (13.02) – 34.37 (12.93)	0.598	6.37 (3.20) – 6.37 (3.58)	1.000

Discussion

This study was performed to weightlifter’s autoregulation resistance training periodization as strategy of continuum zone repetition method implementation. As this study outcomes, performance results were provided on short term weekly periodization in resistance training population. Limitation of study was performance parameter changes are increases to other long term periodization. An of apply of condition in muscle contraction exercise condition principle can be working of different load and repetition regimes into daily auto-regulated resistance training periodization related to progressive multiple set and other interval strategies. The induce of study’ muscle auto-regulated working principle is differences of resistance zone set-up, again load factor to any times can be change in other study. This study was resulted on maximize strength performance gain to weightlifters, thus muscle exercise condition regimes promote general strength and endurance adaptation or/and hypertrophic adaptation responses. Kahraman & Varol (2024) weightlifters’ maximize strength and endurance performance levels investigated to using of continuum zone repetition as high load low repetition and low load high repetition method. As this test outcomes reported to multiple exercise condition as 50/70/85% to 1RM may be perform on strength and hypertrophy zone reach to peak strength performance provided on manipulated set and rest interval. However, autoregulation resistance training with continuum zone repetition method not used in weightlifters to maximize strength condition as performing multiple exercise performance level. This study noted that muscular performance levels change to periodized resistance training model used to continuum zone repetition method to detect strength and endurance development with using seperately hypertrophy and power zone regimes. As this methodological direction of study was reported on autoregulation resistance training is progressive muscle strength and exercise condition to sport-performance and resistance trained population (Mann et al., 2010). Therefore, we reported that multiple sets used in autoregulation resistance training and continuum zone repetition method not provided muscle fatigue accumulation at short term non-linear weekly day to day periodization. Use of autoregulation resistance training were provided on maximize muscle exercise condition of weightlifters, to examine progressive contraction development can be promote high and low load and repetition to weightlifters. Muscular condition of resistance training periodization to enable strength-endurance and muscle contractile potential gain therefore, strategies of incremental loading accomplishment may be repeate continuum zone repetition method as load factor (percentage) tests and repetition (low and high) tests (Kahraman, 2023). Indeed, continuum zone repetition regimes used in within short term auto-regulated hypertrophy and power zone periodization, this study was muscle strength and exercise condition improved to weightlifters, then similar study was same potential gain in different exercise condition (Kahraman et al., 2024). Our study investigated in multi and single joint exercises promote high load low repetition and low load high repetition enable to different resistance zone regimes. Again, specific resistance zones were used in complex weightlift strategies. As combination resistance methods, weightlifters’ continuum zone repetition resistance method can be observe on endurance-

hypertrophy-strength zone periodization with multiple set and 3-5 min interval, thus this results increased muscle strength and exercise condition related load and repetition changes to weightlifters (Kahraman et al., 2024). Specific resistance training methods, high load low repetition and low load high repetition strategies can be support to maximum muscle contraction performance outcomes to weightlifters (Kahraman & Varol, 2024).

In generally, studies showed that related continuum zone repetition periodizations improve maximal strength and endurance, not used to power performance level without autoregulation resistance training. Thus, autoregulation resistance training must be used to loading increases principle to develop strength performance level (Mann et al., 2010), however, continuum zone repetition setted to resistance zone regimes as progressive load increases and repetition changes are combination training set-up and setting to resistance training working principle.

Conclusion

The resistance zone load and repetition periodization not only strength performance but also endurance performance to enable muscle concentric load working principle. In this condition, muscle performance outcomes provided on muscle exercise condition in weightlifters, which perform strength and endurance set session according continuum zone repetition. This study was resulted maximize muscle gain performing hypertrophy zone and power zone autoregulation resistance training forming weightlifters worked on 3 week resistance training, therefore, limitation of study was muscle exercise condition limited over 3 week and 2 day, performance outcomes resulted continuum zone repetition as low load high repetition and high load low repetition. The performance level same exercise performance condition to weightlifters, were performed on muscle responses of indeed exercise condition determined changes of muscle concentric load and maximum number of repetition. Performance level of weightlifters promoted as muscle gain to strength-endurance continuum, however, study was limited only hypertrophy and power zone regime working program.

Kısaltmalar / Abbreviations

- X̄: Mean (Ortalama)
Ss Standard deviation (SD) (Standart sapma)
P P-value (Anlamlılık değeri)

Beyanlar / Declarations

Etik Onay ve Katılım Onayı / Ethics approval and consent to participate

Bu çalışmanın hazırlanma ve yazım sürecinde "Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi" kapsamında bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş olup; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamış ve bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir. Makale ile ilgili doğabilecek her türlü ihlallerde sorumluluk yazara aittir.

In the preparation and writing process of this study, scientific, ethical, and citation principles outlined in the "Directive on Scientific Research and Publication Ethics of Higher Education Institutions" have been strictly followed. No falsification has been made on the collected data, and this study has not been submitted to any other academic publication medium for evaluation. The author assumes full responsibility for any potential violations related to the article.

Veri Ve Materyal Erişilebilirliği / Availability of data and material

Bu çalışmanın bulgularını destekleyen veriler, makul talepler üzerine sorumlu yazardan temin edilebilir. Veri seti yalnızca akademik amaçlar için erişilebilir olacak ve verilerin herhangi bir kullanımı, orijinal çalışmayı referans gösterecek ve katılımcıların gizliliğini koruyacaktır.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request. The dataset will be accessible only for academic purposes, and any use of the data will recognize the original study and maintain the confidentiality of the participants.

Çıkar Çatışması / Competing interests

Yazarlar, bu makalede sunulan çalışmayı etkileyebilecek herhangi bir çıkar çatışması veya kişisel ilişkiye sahip olmadıklarını beyan etmektedirler.

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Yazar Katkıları / Author contributions

Çalışmanın tasarımı ve planlanması: A.Y., B.B.; Veri toplama, analiz ve yorumlama: B.B., A.Y.; Makalenin hazırlanması: B.B., A.Y.; Veri düzenleme, yöntem geliştirme, yazım – özgün taslak, yazım – gözden geçirme ve düzenleme: B.B., A.Y.; Tüm yazarlar, makalenin temel noktalarını eleştirel bir bakış açısıyla değerlendirmiş ve son halini onaylamıştır.

Design and planning of the study: A.Y., B.B.; Data collection, analysis, and interpretation: B.B., A.Y.; Manuscript preparation: B.B., A.Y.; Data organization, methodology development, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing: B.B., A.Y.; All authors critically reviewed the key points of the manuscript and approved the final version.

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